

**A STUDY OF THE ATTITUDE TOWARDS INTERNET AND SOCIAL
NETWORKING SITES AMONG CLASS IX
STUDENTS OF MUMBAI**

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Today internet is one of the most recent advancement in the world of information technology and has been become a useful instrument that has fostered the process of making the world a global village. Internet is a name for a largest and fast World Wide System (WWS) consisting of people, information, and computers which enable to communicate and sharing data among the indefinite number of users at a time scattered all over the world. It is a global network connecting millions of computers more than 190 countries are linked into exchange of data, news and opinion. Internet is a very essential pad of life from advertising and shopping to electronic mails and education.

This is a universal fact that use of internet has great impact on the students' academic achievement and social life. Internet is used for educational purpose by a large number of people. But today large number of people use internet for only social networking websites.

Social networking websites (SNSs) are the fastest growing websites in the 21st century. A social networking site is an online place where a user can create a profile and build personal network that connects him or her to other users. Social networking sites provide web-based application platform for building social networks or social relations among individuals that shared interests or activities to interact via internet or e-mail.

Social networking website is a platform to build social networks or social relations among people who share interests, activities, backgrounds or real-life connections. Social networking sites (SNS) have created a new social dimension where individuals can develop increased levels of their social awareness by keeping in touch with old friends, making new friends, dispense new data or product, and getting information in many more aspects of everyday lives, making one to become more knowledgeable which is very beneficial especially for students.

Brief Review of related Literature:

Sponcil and Gitimou examined social media use among college students and how it affects communication with others, and college students' self-concept. Their results indicated that the sampled college students were using at least one form of social networking website. There was a 0.586 correlation between usage of social media and communication with family and friends. There was a 0.658 correlation between usage social media and self-concept.

Arnett, J. J. (2000) proposes emerging adulthood as a new conception of development for the period from the late teens through the twenties, with a focus on ages 18–25. A theoretical background is presented. Evidence is provided to support the idea that emerging adulthood is a distinct period demographically, subjectively, and in terms of identity explorations. A a cultural context for the idea of emerging adulthood is outlined.

Liu X, Larose R. (2008) examined whether the Internet improves life satisfaction. The study surveyed 195 college students, and a structural model was built to explain effects of the Internet on school life satisfaction using a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). This study established a possible causal mechanism that links life online to an indicator of psychological well-being.

Kesaraporn Wanajak (2011) fills a gap in the international Internet Addiction (IA) literature by developing a consensus definition and diagnostic criteria of IA, investigating the prevalence of IA among Thai secondary school students, as well as

conducting an exploration of the impacts of IA on these students and their prevalence.

Rai (2017) studied the usage pattern of social networking sites (SNS) among the youth. Descriptive design to understand the usage pattern of SNS amongst youth and its impact on their performance and psychological well-being was employed. Different age groups, gender, and regional background were included in the sample. He studied revealed that students have access to internet, 73% are members of at least one SNS. Facebook is very popular, followed by Google +. Majority of the students used SNS mainly for social purposes rather than for educational purposes. SNSs did not affect performance and study habits of the sampled students though it affected language to a certain extent.

Obviously, there has been an increasing trend of Internet Addiction, especially towards social networking sites, among teenage students. So the researcher decided to undertake a short study regarding the Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites among these teenage students of Mumbai.

Thus the problem of the study is stated as follows:

“A Study of the Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites among Class IX Students of Mumbai”

Major Objectives of the Present Study:

- 1) To study the level of Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites amongst Class IX students of Mumbai.
- 2) To compare the Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites amongst Class IX students of Mumbai with reference to the:
 - i. School Board (Maharashtra State Board and CBSE Board)
 - ii. Sex of the students (Female and Male)

Null Hypotheses of the Present Study:

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of the Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites amongst Class IX students of Mumbai with

reference to their:

- 1) School Board (Maharashtra State Board and CBSE Board)
- 2) Sex of the students (Female and Male)

Research Methodology and Participants:

The present study was a descriptive research survey wherein 60 students from CBSE Board and 80 students from Maharashtra State Board schools studying in Class IX were surveyed. There were 70 female and 70 male students who were surveyed in these schools of Mumbai. The sample was collected randomly by visiting schools of Maharashtra State Board and CBSE Board in South Mumbai area. The student teachers of the researcher visited these schools personally for data collection. The schools were requested to cooperate by participating in the survey and only the schools that volunteered and returned the instrument completely filled were taken into consideration for data analysis.

A standardised instrument, the Internet and Social Networking Sites Attitude Scale (ISNSAS) standardised by Dr. Subhash Sarkar and Prasenjit Das, as described below, was selected as it served the purpose of the present research well. The entire data collection process was spread over two months. A lot of persuasion was involved on part of the data collection team to collect data from schools.

The Research Instrument:

The Internet and Social Networking Sites Attitude Scale (ISNSAS) standardised by Dr. Subhash Sarkar and Prasenjit Das, proposes to know the level of the students' attitude towards Internet and Social Networking websites. The scale for attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Websites is constructed keeping two dimensions namely,

- (i) Attitude towards internet.
- (ii) Attitude towards social networking websites.

The scale consists of 50 statements (25 positive and 25 negative) and is applicable for the age range of 15 to 25 years. Five point Rating scale has been used

for statements regarding the attitude of the students towards Internet and Social networking websites, i.e., Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree, Strongly Disagree. The minimum and maximum range of the score is 50 to 250. Negative items are reverse scored.

The coefficient of correlation for Test-Retest Method Reliability for Internet was 0.86 and for Social Networking Sites is 0.84, whereas for full scale it is 0.85. Respondents take 30 to 40 minutes for filling the whole scale.

The Major Findings of the Present Study:

The collected data was tabulated and analysed both through descriptive and inferential analysis (t-test).

	Maharashtra State Board School Students	CBSE Board School Students	Female students	Male students
Mean	156.19	153.72	152.93	157.33
Median	157	151.50	153.5	157.0
Mode	162	147.00	156.0	162.0
Standard Deviation	10.96	12.92	11.2	12.1
Kurtosis	0.76	2.43	1.6	0.9
Skew	-0.33	0.66	-0.5	0.6
Count	80	60	70	70

t-Test Interpretations:

	<i>CBSE Board</i>	<i>Maharashtra State Board</i>
Mean	153.72	156.19
Variance	166.82	120.08
Observations	60	80
Df	138	
t Stat	-1.22	Not Sig. at 0.05 level
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.22	
t Critical two-tail	1.98	

1. The mean score for the CBSE Board students of Class IX on the variable 'Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites' ($M = 153.72$, $SD = 12.92$) did not differ statistically significantly ($t = 1.22$, $df = 138$, two-tailed $p = 0.22$) from that of the Maharashtra State Board students of Class IX ($M = 156.19$, $SD = 10.96$). Thus, the null hypothesis (H_0-1) is supported. The p-value indicates that the probability that the observed results are due to random chance is high.

	<i>Female Students</i>	<i>Male Students</i>
Mean	152.93	157.33
Variance	125.98	147.35
Observations	70	70
df	138	
t Stat	-2.23	Sig. at 0.05 level
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.03	
t Critical two-tail	1.98	

2. The mean score of the Male students on the variable 'Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites' ($M = 157.33$, $SD = 12.1$) is statistically significantly higher ($t = 2.23$, $df = 138$, two-tailed $p = 0.03$) than those of Female students on the same variable ($M = 152.93$, $SD = 11.2$). Thus, the null hypothesis (H_0-2) is rejected. The p-value indicates that the probability that the observed results are due to random chance is low.

Conclusions:

1. There is no statistically significant difference in the mean scores of Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites between Class IX students belonging to CBSE Board schools and those belonging to Maharashtra State Board schools in South Mumbai with reference to the School Boards. Thus, School Boards does not seem to be a contributor towards a favourable Facebook Usage among Class IX students in Mumbai.

2. There is a statistically significant difference in the Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites in Mumbai with reference to the sex of the students of class IX. The scores of Male students is statistically significantly greater than that of Female students. Thus, sex of the students seems to be a contributor to positive and greater favourable Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites Education in Mumbai.

Summary of Major Findings of the Study:

- 1) School Board does not seem to be a contributor towards a favourable Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites among Class IX students in Mumbai.
- 2) Sex of the students seems to be a contributor towards a favourable Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites among Class IX students in Mumbai. Male students are have more favourable Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites among Class IX students in Mumbai.

Scope and Delimitations of the Present Study:

The above major findings of the study are constrained by the limited scope and delimitations of the research which were beyond the control of the researcher. These need to be taken into account, viz.:

- Standardised ready-made instrument (scale) has been employed for the ease of study.
- Paper-pencil test has been employed.
- Volunteering schools participated in the study.
- School students of only Class IX - both females and males - were only considered.
- Time period for data collection has been limited.
- Only two school boards (Maharashtra State Board and CBSE Board) were taken up for the study.
- Only South Mumbai area was considered for data collection.

- The Full Scale was considered in analysis rather than taking the two dimensions separately.

Significance of the Study:

The study, even though being a very short survey, highlights the fact that irrespective of the educational board, there is prevalence of favourable Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites among Class IX students in Mumbai. There is also a significant favourable Attitude towards Internet and Social Networking Sites among Class IX Male students in Mumbai in comparison to the Female students. Future studies which are wider in scope and depth needs to be undertaken for a better understanding of the contemporary phenomena.

References:

- Arnett, J. J. (2000). Emerging adulthood: A theory of development from the late teens through the twenties. *American Psychologist*, 55(5), 469–480.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.55.5.469>
- Hooda, Madhuri and Tyagi, Ankur (2017). Facebook Usage Scale. Agra: National Psychological Corporation.
- Issues and Ideas in Education, Issues and Ideas in Education. (2017). Impact of Social Networking Sites (SNSs): Are Youth affected by its usage?. *Issues and Ideas in Education*. 5. 11-24.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320224866_Impact_of_Social_Networking_Sites_SNSs_Are_Youth_affected_by_its_usage
- John, W. Best and James, V. Kahn (2006). '10th Edition. Research in Education.
- Kesaraporn Wanajak (2011). Internet use and its impact on secondary school students in Chiang Mai, Thailand.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254590783_Internet_use_and_its_impact_on_secondary_school_students_in_Chiang_Mai_Thailand
- Liu X, Larose R. Does using the Internet make people more satisfied with their lives? The effects of the Internet on college students' school life satisfaction.

Cyberpsychol Behav. 2008 Jun; 11(3):310-20. doi: 10.1089/cpb.2007.0040.
PMID: 18537501.

Megan Sponcil and Priscilla Gitimu. Use of social media by college students:
Relationship to communication and self-concept. Journal of Technology
Research. <http://www.aabri.com/manuscripts/121214.pdf>.